

Interconnecting European Smart Grid Infrastructures

The goal of the ERIGrid 2.0 project is to interconnect various European Smart Grid Infrastructures to perform joint experiments and enhance testing capabilities. To this end, a tool-agnostic lab interface has been developed, aka the Universal API (uAPI).

Universal API

Designed a HTTP REST API to cover common functionality in joint multi-lab experiments, such as:

- Data-exchange
- Discovery of available signals
- Participating labs

Joint Experiments

The uAPI has been applied for a proof-of-concept for data exchange using different tools and labs. Tests conducted between the following RIs:

- RWTH (DE) ↔ DTU (DK):
- TUD (NL) and VTT (FI) ↔ RSE (IT)
- TUD (NL) ↔ AIT (AT)

Further Info and Documentation

More information and the code repository is available via the following QR code:

Project Duration:
1 April 2020 -
30 September 2024

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